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A STUDY OF SOCIO ECONOMIC FRONTIERS OF CHILD LABOUR IN KRISHNA DISTRICT OF ANDHRA PRADESH

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Abstract

Child labour is a global phenomenon. It exists both in the developing and developed countries of the world with a difference in cause and magnitude. Its prevalence is more in the developing countries as compared to the developed countries, because the families to which the working children belong, are in an urgent need of income of child labour for their subsistence, where as children in the developed countries are often working for pocket money. Though poverty has been identified as the main reason for the incidence of child labour, a study by the Centre for International Trade, Economics and Environment in India, mentioned that the problem is aggravated by the boycott of goods made by child labourers by the developed nations. The Centre stated that since majority of the children work due to the prevalence of poverty, weaning them away from work by providing free education was not a solution in itself. Rather, the solution will put a heavy burden on the Government exchequer. According to the National Council of Applied Economics Research, "on an average, it will cost the Government RS.67, 740 Crore per annum." There are between 44 and 110 million child labourers in the country, according to the National Sample Survey Organization, which added that a majority of them are from Bihar. Objectives of the Study to analyse the working conditions and problems of child labour who are employed in selected occupations in the selected area and to identify the various reasons which prompt children to work or take up employment, their concern for education, liking to acquire higher skills.

Key Words: Child Labour, Frontiers, Work, Socio, Economic

According to a recent estimate of the International Labour Organisation (ILO), more than 120 million children between the ages of 5-14 are employed as full time labourers around the world. A good number of such children labour in the most hazardous and dangerous industries. In India itself, it is estimated that there are at least 44 million child labourers in the age group of 5-14. More than eighty percent of child labourers in India are employed in the agricultural and non-formal sectors and many are bonded labourers. Most of them are either illiterate or dropped out of school after two or three years.

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¹ UNICEF, (1997) The State of World's Children, Oxford University Press, P.20.

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Eric Edmonds, (2007)⁵ in his empirical work on child labour, reveals a total of 6 peer reviewed journal articles between 1980 and 1990, 65 between 1990 and 2000, and 143 in the first five years of the present decade. The purpose of his essay is to provide a detailed overview of the state of the recent empirical literature on why and how children work as well as the consequences of that work. Section 1 defines terms commonly used in the study of child time allocation and provides a descriptive overview of how children spend their time in low income countries today. Section 2 reviews the case for attention to the most common types of work in which children participate, focusing on that work's impact on schooling, health, as well as externalities associated with that work. Section 3 considers the literature on the determinants of child time allocation such as the influence of local labour markets, family interactions, the net return to schooling, and poverty. Section 5 discusses the limited evidence on different policy options aimed at influencing child labour. Section 6 concludes by emphasizing important research questions requiring additional research such as child and parental agency, the effectiveness of child labour policies, and the determinants of participation in the "worst forms" of child labour.

Sampath Kumar R.D, (2007)⁶ in his book 'Urban Child Labour: Abuse and Neglect' covers wide range of issues pertaining to the nature and extent of child labour in India and various forms of abuse and neglect in family and work settings. Children engaged in the urban work settings such as construction, hotel and tea stalls, two-wheeler motorized service units and domestic service in the city of Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India are covered in the study. Three hundred child labourers, three hundred employers and 210 parents/caretakers were interviewed and data were analyzed and interpreted using large sample tests and other statistical measurements. The book discusses the implications to social policy and social work education.

Objectives of the Study:

- To analyse the working conditions and problems of child labour who are employed in selected occupations in the selected area.
- To identify the various reasons which prompt children to work or take up employment, their concern for education, liking to acquire higher skills.

² ILO,(1996) Child Labour: Targeting the intolerable, International Labour Office, Geneva 1996,p.7

³ Debi S.Saini, (July-September,1994) "Children of a Lesser God, Child Labour Law and Compulsory Primary Education" Social Action,Vol.44.No.3,p.2

⁴ The Hindu Business Line, 3 January 2000.

⁵ Eric Edmonds, (2007), 'Child Labour', NBER Working Paper No. 12926, Issued in February 2007, NBER Program (s)

⁶ Sampath Kumar, R.D,(2007). Urban Child Labour: Abuse and Neglect, the Associated Publishers, Delhi.

Results and Discussions

The investigator collects information from the respondent, who is not essentially the head of the household. But the demographic profile of the respondent is same as that of the family. Hence, we collected the demographic profile of the child labour from the respondent himself. Out of 235 households surveyed 184 respondents are head of the household and rest 51 respondents are not the head of the family. In percentage terms this is 80.4 and 21.7 percent respectively. This fact is detailed in Table 1. Higher percentage of respondents (78.2) being the head of the households ensures reliability of the data under sample survey.

The broad age group wise distribution of the respondents is given in Table 2, 121 respondents are in the age group of 21-40, and 91 respondents are above 40 years of age. Only 23 respondents are below the age of 20. This may be due to the temporary absence of head of the household. These respondents very often take the responsibility of the family as they are the identified Child Labourers of the household. Since 90.2 percent of the respondents are in a responsible age group, we expect trustworthy result from the survey.

From the study it is clear that maximum number of members of the households covered under the study is engaged as casual labourers, i.e. 592 cases and 120 as self employed. This clearly shows that they have no option to choose but join in the labour force whatever opportunity is available in the vicinity. Really it is a pitiable situation as shown in the table 3

Table-4 depicts the primary source of income of the households surveyed by the investigator. Maximum number of families earned their livelihood by engaging themselves in casual Labour. Next important source of income is the agriculture. These two activities together covered 95 percent of the households surveyed. Only ten families have earned their income from migrant remittance, services, business, etc.

Findings and Conclusions

This chapter makes an attempt to provide a brief summary of the main findings of the present study and to suggest some suitable, possible and feasible policies and strategies which could be adopted for the economic development of working children, to gradually reduce the extent of child labour, and to provide alternative opportunities for skill, work experience and economic stability.

Child labour is economically unsound, psychologically disastrous, physically dangerous and harmful to the child. Children are exploited and exposed to hazardous working conditions and paid a pittance for their long-hours of work. These are forced to forego education shouldering responsibilities beyond their age. The need to understand the present day realities of child labour is strongly relevant since it is within these orientations that laws for children get drafted, enacted, interpreted, enforced, and debated. A closer look at the existing scenario indicates that the policies and priorities at the macro level are changing more rapidly than the situation of child labour and the conditions of their work. At the ground level, children continue to work for long hours in an extremely harmful environment, poorly paid or unpaid, and are very often abused by their employers and co-workers. Although constant validation of existing policies against the situational realities of child labour is called for evidence shows that there is very little scope for children (and those who work on their behalf) to be heard while policies which affect them directly are being framed meant for the betterment of children either remain on paper or compound the very problems which they seek to address.

After independence, the Government of India has displayed keen concern for the well-being of the child. Under the central and state Governments children Acts, a chain of residential welfare institutions have been set up for children who are compelled to join the labour force in urban centers. Under its policy resolution on children (1974), the union Government has constituted a national children's board at the highest level with the prime minister as its president to coordinate, plan, implement and evaluate child welfare programmes in the country. In 1979, it set up a committee on child labour to examine the problem in depth and suggest remedial measures. These and other welfare measures notwithstanding the problem of child labour is bound to persist on the Indian scene for decades to come. As long as poverty exists, child labour too will exist and any attempt to abolish it

totally through legal recourse would not be successful. A total legal abolition of child labour, moreover, may generate unintended and undesirable social consequences. The only rational alternative seems to be to ban child labour in certain hazardous areas and ameliorate the conditions of work in others so that child labour ceases to be inimical to the child's growth and development. Legal instruments on child labour have existed in some form or other since over a hundred years. Yet they have made very little impact on the situation of working children, in particular, as well as on the problem of child labour as a whole.

What first strikes one is the fact that those young workers typically seen in various work settings are predominantly from a narrow age range of pre-adolescent and early adolescent stage of life cycle. From a development perspective, this age is a critical moment in the child's socialization and in the formation of self-identity and self esteem that will be carried into adulthood. Much of what the person will be in society later on is cast during this period. The implication is that actions to protect working children should be attractive and appropriate, above all to this age group.

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List of Tables

Table -1
Sample Profile of Head of the Household

Item	Number	Percent
Respondent is head of the Household	184	78.2
Respondent is not head of the Household	51	21.7
Total	235	100

Source: Primary data

Table-2
Profile of the Age of the Respondents

Age of the Respondent	Number	Percent
Less than 20	23	9.8
21-40	121	51.5
Above 40	91	38.7
Total	235	100

Source: Primary data

Table-3
Working Status of the members of the Household (>6 age)

Item	Number	Percent
Self-Employed	120	16.3
Causal Labour	592	80.2
Hired Labour	12	1.6
Service	2	0.3
Other	12	1.6
Total	738	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table-4
Primary Source of Income

Source of Income	Number	Percent
Agriculture	78	33.2
Casual Labour	147	62.6
Migrant Remittance	1	0.4
Services	3	1.3
Business	3	1.3
Any Other	3	1.3
Total	235	100

Source: Primary Data